

THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY FROM DRY TO WATER-SATURATED CONDITIONS: AN ANALYTICAL APPROACH

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Abstract

This work aims at developing a quick and reliable approach to convert thermal conductivity from dry to water-saturation conditions. The analytical approach shows a relative error between experimental and analytical values up to 10 %. This is an acceptable error to indirectly infer the thermal conductivity under water-saturation conditions.

1. Introduction

The process of water saturation of rock samples regardless of their porosity is time-consuming. It can take up to 48 h in a vacuum chamber to saturate rock samples. Moreover, the evaluation of the thermal conductivity at water-saturated conditions can easily be affected by experimental errors and not all the devices can carry out such analyses. For example, the optical scanning technique is more suited for dry rocks than for water-saturated samples. The conversion of dry bulk thermal conductivity into its respective saturated value without applying the saturation procedure can be advantageous. The goal of this work is to demonstrate an analytical approach for this conversion within a relative error up to 10 %. The approach selected is based on the mixing mean models: arithmetic, harmonic and geometric means (e.g., Fuchs et al. 2013).

2. Methods and techniques

Thermal conductivity of a set of 31 crystalline rock samples (paragneiss, diorite, gabbro, tonalite, granite) was evaluated at both dry and water-saturated conditions. The instrument used to evaluate the thermal conductivity is the FOX50 Heat Flow Meter. It analyses thermal conductivity based on the steady state method and the guarded heat flow meter technique, and as an accuracy up to 3 % (e.g., Raymond et al. 2017). Then, the effective porosity was evaluated with a combined gas permeameter-porosimeter AP-608 from Core Test following Boyle's law (e.g., Raymond et al. 2017).

Assuming rocks are represented by a two-phase system composed of pore fluid and solids, the following mixing

models can be used to relate thermal conductivity and porosity:

- Arithmetic mean

$$\lambda = \phi\lambda_f + (1-\phi)\lambda_s \quad (1)$$

- Harmonic mean

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{\frac{\phi}{\lambda_f} + \frac{(1-\phi)}{\lambda_s}} \quad (2)$$

- Geometric mean

$$\lambda = \lambda_f^\phi \times \lambda_s^{(1-\phi)} \quad (3)$$

where λ ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) is thermal conductivity and ϕ (%) is porosity. The subscripts f and s refer to the fluid-phase filling the rock voids and the solid phase, respectively.

The proposed analytical approach takes Eqs. 1 to 3 and resolves them on the basis of a system of equations for dry and saturated conditions, allowing to calculate thermal conductivity under saturated conditions:

- Arithmetic mean

$$\begin{cases} \lambda_{\text{dry}} = \phi\lambda_{\text{air}} + (1-\phi)\lambda_s \\ \lambda_{\text{sat}} = \phi\lambda_{\text{water}} + (1-\phi)\lambda_s \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

- Harmonic mean

$$\begin{cases} \lambda_{\text{dry}} = \frac{1}{\frac{\phi}{\lambda_{\text{air}}} + \frac{(1-\phi)}{\lambda_s}} \\ \lambda_{\text{sat}} = \frac{1}{\frac{\phi}{\lambda_{\text{water}}} + \frac{(1-\phi)}{\lambda_s}} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

- Geometric mean

$$\begin{cases} \lambda_{\text{dry}} = \lambda_{\text{air}}^\phi \times \lambda_s^{(1-\phi)} \\ \lambda_{\text{sat}} = \lambda_{\text{water}}^\phi \times \lambda_s^{(1-\phi)} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Here, the subscripts dry and sat stand for the state at which thermal conductivity was evaluated, which are respectively, dry and water saturated. Air and water are related with the fluid filling the sample voids.

The mean relative error (MRE) was calculated to assess the inherent error of using these relationships. The *MRE* is determined as:

$$MRE = \frac{\lambda_{exp} - \lambda_{cal}}{\lambda_{exp}} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

where the subscripts exp and cal stand for the thermal conductivity evaluated and calculated, respectively.

3. Results

The results reveal an increase in thermal conductivity from dry to water-saturated state in most of the lithological groups (**Table 1**). On average, the thermal conductivity increases by 18 % for the paragneiss, 11 % for the diorite, 10 % for the gabbro, 15 % for the tonalite, and decreases by 2 % for the granite. This decrease is thought to be due to the intrinsic accuracy of the device rather than the experimental procedure itself.

Table 1 Group averaged values for each thermophysical parameter

Lithology	λ_{dry}	λ_{sat}	Φ
	(W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)		(%)
Paragneiss	2.26	2.67	2.81
Diorite	2.78	3.08	2.05
Gabbro	2.93	3.21	2.05
Tonalite	3.02	3.47	2.29
Granite	3.22	3.17	2.85

A comparison of thermal conductivity with the effective porosity reveals that samples with a low effective porosity show a smaller increase in thermal conductivity associated to saturation than more porous samples.

Applying arithmetic and harmonic mean models (Eq. 4, 5) to convert thermal conductivity from dry to water-saturated conditions leads to a relative error of more than 20 %. Smaller relative error is obtained by applying the geometric mean model (Eq. 6; **Table 2**).

Table 2 Thermal conductivity at water-saturation conditions, experimental vs analytical methods

Lithology	λ_{exp}	λ_{cal}	<i>MRE</i>
	(W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)		(%)
Paragneiss	2.67	2.46	8
Diorite	3.08	2.96	4
Gabbro	3.21	3.12	3
Tonalite	3.47	3.23	7
Granite	3.17	3.51	-11

The use of this analytical approach, for this dataset, leads to a relative error up to 10 %. This analysis points that this simple analytical approach can be a helpful tool to convert thermal conductivity from dry to water-saturated conditions.

4. Discussion

Fuchs et al. (2013) did a similar study with sedimentary rocks and concluded that the geometric mean model displays the best correspondence between measured and calculated thermal conductivity. However, these authors indicated that the relation was not fully satisfactory. Their approach relied on correction equations calculated based on the statistical data to improve the fit of the models. For this study, the relationship is satisfying. However, further work is needed to verify if the relative error stays low when applying the same approach to other rock types.

Additionally, this analytical approach can also be used to evaluate the effect of temperature on thermal conductivity of water-saturated samples. Carrying out such analysis at different temperature ranges is only possible for samples at dry state, due to water evaporation. However, with this analytical approach, saturated thermal conductivity can be calculated from dry thermal conductivity evaluated at high temperature.

5. Conclusions

A quick and reliable approach to convert thermal conductivity from dry state to water-saturation conditions was described in this work. The thermal conductivity inferred indirectly by this analytical approach has a relative error up to 10 % when compared with the experimental procedure.

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